

Patterns of vertical distribution and temporal changes of rocky
shore intertidal limpets in rock pools at Dwesa-Cwebe Nature
Reserve

By

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Abstract

This study investigated the vertical distribution and temporal changes of limpet species. Species diversity was measured in terms of number of limpet species. Sampling was conducted at Dwesa-Cwebe Nature Reserve and two sites with approximately 1.5 km apart were selected. In each site, three rock pools were chosen: MLWS (mid low water shore), MHWS (mid high water shore) and HWS (high water shore). ANOVA results revealed that no significant differences on species diversity, implying the importance of biological processes such as recruitment rather than physical processes. Despite seasonal differences in environmental conditions, the limpet species occurred across the three shore heights. Although there were significant differences in mean sizes (shell lengths) in three (*Cellana capensis*, *Siphonaria serrata* *Helcion concolor*) out of seven limpet species found, there were significant interaction of season and site, indicating that the mean shell length had significant effects in some seasons but not others. Where there were significant differences, mean shell lengths decreased with a decrease in shore height and vice versa. Mean temperatures and salinities increased significantly with an increase in height. They also showed significant differences among seasons and between sites, suggesting temporal and spatial variations on small scales (1.5 km).

Key words: Limpets, intertidal zone, rock pools, distribution, species diversity, size structure, temporal changes, spatial changes

1. Introduction

Limpets are molluscs with a cap-shaped shell and a suction cup-like foot (Branch *et al.* 2002). Their shell covers the animal completely and maybe closely applied to the substratum to prevent loss of water during exposure. The shell also protects against abrasion and predation (Branch 1971). There are two different kinds of limpets, which are the true limpets of the subclass Prosobranchia, which consists of a ring of gills around the foot. The second subclass is Pulmonata which lack gills and are closely related to land snails. This study is specifically about true limpets which are marine gastropod molluscs in the order Patellogastropoda (Branch *et al.* 2002). Approximately 80 species of its kind have been recorded and they live on the rocky coast of all oceans world-wide. South African limpets are more abundant in the east coast due to very warm water caused by the Agulhas Current which sweeps warm water from the subtropics down the east coast (Branch *et al.* 2002). Species like *Patella granularis* grow faster in the cold west coast than in warmer water and nutrient value of organic depositions (Branch 1974).

The limpets feed by grazing on microalgae attached securely to the rocky substrate (Cook & Cook 1981, Lasiak & White 1993). Some species of limpets return to the spot on the rock known as a home scar just before the tide recedes. These species usually form a scar in a rock. For instance some members of the genus *Patella* tend to occupy a fixed position on the shore allowing a well defined scar on the substrate to be formed (Branch 1971, Branch 1975a). This behaviour allows them to form a better seal to the rock and may help protect from either predation or desiccation (Branch 1971).

Limpets reproduce by means of broadcast spawning whereby the males and females release a large number of sperms and eggs in water and then fertilization occurs by chance (Branch 1971). Their life-span also differs for instance, *Cellana capensis* can live up to 6 years while *Scutellastra cochlear* can live up to 25 years (Branch 1994). Most limpets are preferred as food item by human beings and their shells are used to make ornaments (Lasiak & White 1993).

The limpets usually inhabit the intertidal zone, which is at the boundary between marine and terrestrial ecosystem. The environment in the intertidal zone is determined by the daily cycle of tides. The action of tides creates a vertical gradient of physical conditions which influences the distribution of organisms (Branch & Branch 1981, Hayes 2007). Intertidal zone is divided into high, mid and low water shore. All these zones consist of rock pools which are formed when high tide comes in over a rocky shore and fills depressions in the ground which turn into isolated pools as water retreats (Branch & Branch 1981). Rock pools are dynamic and intermittently isolated habitats in the rocky intertidal zone. Organisms inhabiting rock pools are subjected to stressful environmental conditions during the low-water period with large fluctuations over short temporal scales in physico-chemical parameters such as temperature, salinity, oxygen, carbon dioxide and pH (Underwood & Skilleter 1996; Martins *et al.* 2007). Pools on the upper shore are exposed to longer periods of emersion and hence experience greater variability in environmental conditions (Martins *et al.* 2007).

According to Taylor (1988), animals inhabiting littoral rock pools are faced with a number of problems which they must overcome in order to survive successfully. The rock pool environment is quite different from the shallow sublittoral zone. The oxygen concentration of rock pools varied according to the time of day. Each rock pool is unique and therefore it is not possible to predict which diel variation the organism will be exposed to (Underwood & Skilleter 1996). The effect of climatic factors on conditions within rock pools do count. For instance, the changes in the weather can produce marked differences in environmental days and an example is that the temperature of rock pools can be significantly higher on sunny days than on cloudy days. There is seasonal variation in the rock pool environment (Taylor 1988).

Some studies indicated that in bare rocks or emergent rocks there is a variation in species distribution as the height of shore increases (Benedetti-Cecchi *et al.* 1999; Underwood 2004). A similar study was conducted by Otaiza and Santelices (1985) which aimed at determining the density and size of chitons (which are also intertidal grazers) at different levels on the intertidal rock, in pools and on boulders. The species showed segregation according to a range of increasing frequency of water movement in pools. It was found that water movement may be a significant factor in setting the lower limits of distribution of these organisms for instance as small sized species and a few individuals of large sized species were found higher on rock walls or in zones where water movement was less and large chitons occurred in zones of greater impact. Therefore the distribution of chitons was determined by wave action (Otaiza & Santelices 1985).

Many studies done are on zonation in emergent rock (Branch 1971; Vermeij 1972) but little is known about zonation in rock pools. The main aim of this study was to investigate whether rock pools show a decrease in species diversity with increasing height above sea level as is common for rocky shore environment. In addition, physico-chemical conditions like salinity and temperature were monitored so as to investigate their effect on both species diversity and size structure of these limpets with increasing height above sea level. Specific objectives of the study were to:

- i) Determine the diversity of limpets in rock pools at mid-low, mid-high and high water shores.
- ii) Compare the diversity of limpets among heights of the shore in each site.
- iii) Determine the size structure of limpets in different shore heights to allow comparison.
- iv) Investigate how temperature affects species diversity and size structure.
- v) Examine how salinity affects species diversity and size structure.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The study was conducted at Dwesa-Cwebe Nature Reserve (32°18'S, 28°50'E) which is a marine protected area situated in the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa (Fig.1).

Fig. 1: Map showing Dwesa-Cwebe Nature Reserve in the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa.

2.2 Sampling procedure

Sampling took place once in each of the four seasons (autumn, winter, spring and summer 2008) during spring low tide. Two sites which were about 1.5 km apart were selected and each site consisted of three heights which were the mid low, mid high and high water shores. The mid low water shore (MLWS) was characterized by the presence of barnacles, mid high water shore (MHWS) was characterized by mixture of barnacles and oysters and the high water shore (HWS) was characterized by littorina. Three rock pools were randomly chosen in each tidal zone and a square quadrat of 50 x 50 cm was placed in each rock pool and the number of species within each quadrat in each height were counted and recorded. Although each rock pool was unique, their areas ranged between 2.5 – 4.5 m² and depth ranging between 3 – 4 cm. Pool shape was not taken into consideration, though only pools with well-defined boundaries were selected. This was done during spring low tide. The species diversity was measured in terms number of different limpet species found in each rock pool. The total shell length of individual limpets was measured to the nearest 0.05mm, using Vernier calipers. This was then compared in all four seasons of the year.

2.3 Physico-chemical parameters

During the sampling period, the water temperature and salinity of rock pool in each site at each height were measured. The water temperature was measured using thermometer and the salinity was measured using refractometer which was rinsed with distilled water after use in each occasion. All measurements from salinity and temperature were taken within 30 minutes of low tide.

2.5 Statistical analysis

A 3-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used in order to test the effect of site, height and season on species diversity and size structure of limpets. A 3-way Analyses of Variance (ANOVA) was also used to test the effect of temperature and salinity in the distribution of limpets in different seasons, sites and heights. Prior to the use of ANOVA, the data were tested for normality and homogeneity of variance using Chochrans' and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests (Zar 1996; Underwood 1997), respectively.

3. Results

3.1 Species diversity

The results of a three-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) revealed that heights, sites and season had no significant effects ($p > 0.05$) on limpet diversity. The interaction between season and height and between season and site also showed no significant difference (Table 1). In all sites the following species of limpets were found: *Cellana capensis*, *Siphonaria capensis*, *Siphonaria serrata*, *Helcion concolor*, *Scutellastra longicosta*, *Helcion pectunculus* and *Fissurella mutabilis* and their distribution (Tables 2 to 5). The species *Cellana capensis*, *Siphonaria capensis*, *Siphonaria serrata* and *Helcion concolor* were generally distributed across the heights and through seasons.

Table 1: Results of the 3-way ANOVA based on species diversity estimates of limpets at different levels along the shore.

Source of variance	SS	df	MS	F	p
Season	3.17	3	1.06	1.55	0.46
Site	0.00	1	0.00	0.00	1.00
Height	0.75	2	0.37	0.49	0.63
Season x Site	2.00	3	0.67	0.89	0.49
Season x Height	4.58	6	0.76	1.02	0.48
Error	6.00	8	0.75		

Table 2: The distribution of limpets in autumn at each site. (+ denotes species present in the shore level).

Species name	Site 1			Site 2		
	MLWS	MHWS	HWS	MLWS	MHWS	HWS
<i>Cellana capensis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	
<i>Siphonaria capensis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Siphonaria serrata</i>	+	+	+	+		+
<i>Helcion concolor</i>	+		+		+	
<i>Scutellastra longicosta</i>						
<i>Helcion pectunculus</i>						
<i>Fissurella mutabillis</i>						

Table 3: The distribution of limpets in winter at each site. (+ denotes species present in the shore level).

Species name	Site 1			Site 2		
	MLWS	MHWS	HWS	MLWS	MHWS	HWS
<i>Cellana capensis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Siphonaria capensis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Siphonaria serrata</i>	+	+	+	+		
<i>Helcion concolor</i>				+	+	+
<i>Scutellastra longicosta</i>						
<i>Helcion pectunculus</i>						
<i>Fissurella mutabillis</i>						

Table 4: The distribution of limpets in spring at each site. (+ denotes species present in the shore level).

Species name	Site 1			Site 2		
	MLWS	MHWS	HWS	MLWS	MHWS	HWS
<i>Cellana capensis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Siphonaria capensis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Siphonaria serrata</i>	+	+	+		+	
<i>Helcion concolor</i>		+		+	+	+
<i>Scutellastra longicosta</i>	+					
<i>Helcion pectunculus</i>					+	
<i>Fissurella mutabilis</i>					+	

Table 5: The distribution of limpets in summer at each site. (+ denotes species present in the shore level).

Species name	Site 1			Site 2		
	MLWS	MHWS	HWS	MLWS	MHWS	HWS
<i>Cellana capensis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Siphonaria capensis</i>	+	+		+	+	+
<i>Siphonaria serrata</i>			+			+
<i>Helcion concolor</i>				+		+
<i>Scutellastra longicosta</i>						
<i>Helcion pectunculus</i>	+	+				
<i>Fissurella mutabilis</i>						

3.2 Size structure

ANOVA results revealed no significant effects on mean shell lengths of *Siphonaria capensis*, *Scutellastra longicosta*, *Helcion pectunculus* and *Fissurella mutabilis* (Tables 6 to 9). However, there were significant ($p < 0.05$) effects on mean shell lengths of *Cellana capensis*, *Siphonaria serrata* and *Helcion concolor* (Tables 10, 11 and 12).

Table 6: Results of the 3-way ANOVA based on the mean shell length estimates of *Siphonaria capensis*.

Source of variance	SS	df	MS	F	p
Season	5801	3	1933.54	0.57	0.69
Site	10573	1	10572.76	1.61	0.28
Height	2822	2	1410.92	1.25	0.32
Season x Site	20320	3	6773.50	1.32	0.27
Season x Height	4827	6	804.42	0.16	0.99
Error	2789583	545	5118.50		

Table 7: Results of the 3-way ANOVA based on the mean shell length estimates of *Scutellastra longicosta*.

Source of variance	SS	df	MS	F	p
Season	30.25	3	10.08	1.00	0.54
Site	10.08	1	10.08	1.00	0.39
Height	20.17	2	10.08	1.00	0.42
Season x Site	30.25	3	10.08	1.00	0.41
Season x Height	60.50	6	10.08	1.00	0.44
Error	322.67	32	10.08		

Table 8: Results of the 3-way ANOVA based on the mean shell length estimates of *Fissurella mutabilis*.

Source of variance	SS	df	MS	F	p
Season	2.64	3	0.88	1.00	0.54
Site	0.88	1	0.88	1.00	0.39
Height	1.76	2	0.88	1.00	0.42
Season x Site	2.64	3	0.88	1.00	0.41
Season x Height	5.28	6	0.88	1.00	0.44
Error	28.17	32	0.88		

Table 9: Results of the 3-way ANOVA based on the mean shell length estimates of *Helcion pectunculus*.

Source of variance	SS	df	MS	F	p
Season	288.21	3	96.07	1.37	0.38
Site	2.97	1	2.97	0.06	0.82
Height	95.28	2	47.64	0.86	0.47
Season x Site	142.00	3	47.33	1.44	0.25
Season x Height	332.87	6	55.48	1.69	0.15
Error	1148.88	35	32.83		

3.2.1 *Cellana capensis*

There were significant ($p < 0.05$) effects of site and height including the interactions between season and site and between season and height (Table 10). Both sites were found to be significantly different with greatest and smallest mean shell length of 18.46 ± 0.16 and 14.90 ± 0.13 , found in site 2 and site 1, respectively (Fig. 2).

Season and height

The interaction of season and height had a significant effect on size structure of *C. capensis* in all seasons except summer. The HWS (21.60 ± 0.45) in autumn had the greatest sizes as compared to MHWS (15.01 ± 0.30). The HWS (24.11 ± 0.58) in winter had the greatest sizes and the MLWS (13.53 ± 0.21) still in winter had the smallest sizes (Fig. 3).

Table 10: Results of the 3-way ANOVA based on the mean shell length estimates of *Cellana capensis* (* denotes significance at $p < 0.05$).

Source of variance	SS	df	MS	F	p
Season	1044.70	3	348.20	0.58	0.64
Site	8597.00	1	8597.00	19.38	0.02*
Height	6874.20	2	3437.10	7.10	0.03*
Season x Site	1335.30	3	445.10	21.68	0.00*
Season x Height	2984.90	6	497.50	24.23	0.00*
Error	64543.30	3144	20.50		

Fig. 2: Mean (+SE) shell length of *Cellana capensis* in each season at each site.

(*indicates where there was a significant difference at $p < 0.05$).

Fig. 3: Mean (+SE) shell length of *Cellana capensis* in each season at each height.

(*indicates where there was a significant difference at $p < 0.05$).

3.2.2 *Siphonaria serrata*

The mean shell length showed significant difference ($p < 0.05$) on the interaction between season and height (Table 11). Summer was found to be more significantly different with HWS (14.28 ± 1.03) having the biggest sizes as compared to MHWS (0.00 ± 3.00) (Fig. 4).

Table 11: Results of the 3-way ANOVA based on the mean shell length estimates of *Siphonaria serrata* (* denotes significance at $p < 0.05$).

Source of variance	SS	df	MS	F	p
Season	386.70	3	128.90	1.11	0.41
Site	300.19	1	300.19	6.62	0.08
Height	260.56	2	130.28	1.37	0.32
Season x Site	146.30	3	48.77	2.71	0.05
Season x Height	659.60	6	109.93	6.12	0.00*
Error	2856.93	159	17.97		

Fig. 4: Mean (+SE) shell length of *Siphonaria serrata* in each season at each height.

(*indicates where there was a significant difference at $p < 0.05$).

3.2.3 *Helcion concolor*

The mean shell length showed significant difference ($p < 0.05$) on the interaction between season and site (Table 12). Winter revealed that mean sizes in site 2 (19.64 ± 2.11) were significantly bigger than mean sizes in site 1 (0.01 ± 4.67) (Fig. 5).

Table 12: Results of the 3-way ANOVA based on the mean shell length estimates of *Helcion concolor* (* denotes significance at $p < 0.05$).

Source of variance	SS	df	MS	F	p
Season	697.52	3	232.51	0.89	0.54
Site	538.10	1	538.10	2.03	0.25
Height	258.05	2	129.03	2.03	0.20
Season x Site	832.89	3	277.63	4.35	0.01*
Season x Height	381.30	6	63.56	1.00	0.44
Error	2358.87	37	63.75		

Fig. 5: Mean (+SE) shell length of *Helcion concolor* in each season at each site.

(*indicates where there was a significant difference at $p < 0.05$).

3.3 Physico-chemical parameters

3.3.1 Temperature

There were significant ($p < 0.05$) effect of height including the season/site interaction (Table 13). Other factors were not significantly different. There was a significant ($p < 0.05$) height effect on mean water temperature (Table 13). Post-hoc tests revealed significant difference between MLWS and HWS with the latter being greater than the former (Fig. 6). The highest and lowest mean temperature was 25.38 ± 0.58 and 20.68 ± 0.58 found at HWS and MLWS, respectively.

Season and site

There was a gradual increase in mean water temperature from the beginning of the experiment until the end of the experiment for site 2. Except for the last season (summer), site 1 also showed the same trend. Post-hoc tests showed significance between site 1 and site 2 only in summer with site 2 being greater than site 1. There was no significant

difference ($p > 0.05$) in the mean water temperatures in seasons, sites and in the interaction between season and height. The significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was found in the mean temperatures in height and in the interaction between season and site.

The interaction between the season and site, showed significant differences between site 1 and 2 in summer with site 2 being greater than site 1. This reflected the fact that the mean temperature at site 1 was 19.00 ± 1.07 while at site 2 was (28.10 ± 1.07) (Fig. 7).

Table 13: Results of the 3-way ANOVA based on the mean water temperature estimates in each site at each height. (* denotes significance at $p < 0.05$).

Source of variance	SS	df	MS	F	p
Season	25.55	3	8.52	0.27	0.84
Site	32.90	1	32.90	1.02	0.39
Height	88.73	2	44.36	16.21	0.00*
Season x Site	96.46	3	32.15	9.41	0.01*
Season x Height	16.42	6	2.74	0.80	0.60
Error	27.35	8	3.42		

Fig. 6: Mean (+SE) temperature of each rock pool at shore levels. Letters above the bars indicate homogenous groups.

Fig. 7: Mean (+SE) temperature over seasons at each site. (*indicates where there was a significant difference at $p < 0.05$).

3.3.2 Salinity

There was a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the mean salinity in seasons, sites and height (Table 14). All seasons were significantly different with summer (49.43 ± 0.59) having the highest salinity and winter (41.68 ± 0.59) with the lowest salinity (Fig. 8). There was a significant difference in all sites with site 2 (46.63 ± 0.26) having the highest salinity and site 1 (43.70 ± 0.26) with the lowest salinity (Fig. 9).

All the heights were found to be significantly different with HWS (47.09 ± 0.30) having the highest salinity and the MLWS (42.89 ± 0.30) having the lowest salinity (Fig. 10).

Table 14: Results of the 3-way ANOVA based on the mean salinity estimates (* denotes significance at $p < 0.05$).

Source of variance	SS	df	MS	F	p
Season	206.41	3	68.80	32.45	0.02*
Site	32.67	1	32.67	14.50	0.03*
Height	71.26	2	35.63	50.87	0.00*
Season x Site	6.76	3	2.25	2.71	0.12
Season x Height	4.20	6	0.70	0.84	0.57
Error	6.66	8	0.83		

Fig. 8: Mean (+SE) salinity of each rock pool in each site overtime. Letters above the bars indicate homogenous groups.

Fig. 9: Overall mean (+SE) salinity of rock pools in each site. Letters above the bars indicate homogenous groups.

Fig. 10: Mean (+SE) salinity of each rock pool at each height. Letters above the bars indicate homogenous groups.

4. Discussion

The results from this study showed that season, site and height of the shore had no effect on species diversity. Therefore, this implies that limpets found on rock pools are distributed evenly or almost the same regardless of the season, site and height in which they are found. However, this completely disagrees with some studies conducted on emergent rock. For instance, according to Branch (1971) the distribution of limpets in the intertidal zone is determined by their tolerance to salinity, temperature, desiccation, wave action, light, substrate, acclimation and availability of food. These are other factors which determine where a species can be found depending on its ability to tolerate the physical and biological stresses. In an intertidal zone, extreme temperatures usually occur in the high water shore (HWS) and therefore, animals which cannot withstand extreme temperatures, inhabit the mid low water shore (MLWS). Unless an animal is capable of acclimation (e.g. high level limpet *Patella vulgate*), tends to have lower respiratory rate during summer when compared to low level species (Davies 1966; 1967 cited in Branch 1971).

According to Underwood (2000) a two dimensional space is a resource required by almost all intertidal rocky shore species either directly or indirectly as an absolute need to space on which to settle and grow or as a relative need for space over which to feed. Therefore Espinosa *et al.* (2006) stated that food and space are the major resources competed for by the limpets. Competition is the other factor influencing limpet distribution this is due to limited food resources in rocky shores (Nakai *et al.* 2006).

The high-shore limpets are more tolerant to high temperatures (Branch 1981). Therefore, only those animals tolerant to these extreme temperatures can exist in this zone while those which cannot tolerate these temperatures, usually prefer low shore whereby they get to be exposed only for a short while. According to Hayes (2007), temperatures tend to vary within the four seasons of the year with summer having the highest temperatures. In contrary, this study revealed very low temperatures in summer.

The temperature was significantly different between heights. Temperature increased with an increase in height most probably due to the fact that low waters shores are most of the time immersed in water as compared to high water shores, which are frequently exposed and hardly receive cool sea water and that would result in experiencing more sunlight and therefore result in extreme temperatures (Menconi *et al.* 1999; Huang *et al.* 2006). When temperatures are high, water tends to evaporate resulting in more concentrated mediums and therefore increased salinities.

Sites showed significant differences in salinities, with site 2 having the highest salinities. Different heights also exhibited different salinities most probably due to the temperatures experienced in these heights which determine the rate of evaporation and therefore the degree of salinity, with HWS having the highest salinities due to extreme temperatures experienced. High water shores tend to experience high levels of salinity and therefore, organisms in these regions should be able to tolerate high salinities. Salinities also showed an increase with increasing height and this is due to wave exposure and evaporation which increases and results in more concentrated salinities. In this study,

salinity was found to be affected by the season, site and height. Different seasons had different mean salinities. This was attributed to different conditions experienced during different seasons. Similarly, Hayes (2007) working on algae, reported that some seasons experienced extreme temperatures and some drought conditions.

Conclusion

This study suggests that there is no increase in species diversity with the increasing height above sea level despite temperature and salinity fluctuations. There was no clear pattern of vertical distribution established. Therefore further studies on the effect of predation in regulating zonation in rock pools are suggested.

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